

Estimating the Effect on Happiness through Question Randomization: An Application to Blood Donation

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Abstract:

This study examines the impact of blood donation on happiness among blood donors at Phulo Jhano Medical College & Hospital, Dumka, Jharkhand. The study employs question randomization to address the potential order effects in survey response. The research involved 400 participants (200 donors & 200 non donors) and demonstrated that blood donors report significantly higher happiness score compared to non-donors. The donors age ranged from 18 years to 50 years. The average age was 26 years. The findings of the study support the psychological benefits of altruistic behavior, such as blood donation, and suggest a notable positive correlation between such activities and increased personal well-being. This study underscores the potential for integrating these findings into public health strategies to promote blood donation, highlighting not only its critical role in healthcare but also its capacity to enhance donor happiness.

Keywords: Blood Donation, Happiness, Altruism, Question Randomization.

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Introduction

The concept of happiness and its determinants remains a central theme in psychological research and public policy [1]. Understanding what influences happiness can guide the development of interventions aimed at improving individual well-being. Blood donation, a selfless act, has been hypothesized to influence the donor's emotional and psychological state, potentially enhancing their sense of happiness and life satisfaction [2]. However, measuring such effects is complex due to the subjective nature of happiness and the varying impacts of external activities on individuals' emotional states.

This study employs a novel methodological approach—question randomization—to estimate the effect of blood donation on happiness. The question randomization technique, often used in survey methodology, involves varying the order of questions for different respondents [3]. This can help in mitigating the biases associated with question order effects, thus providing a more accurate measure of the true impact of certain activities on happiness. By applying this technique, the study aims to isolate the specific contribution of blood donation to overall happiness from other confounding variables [4,5].

The objective of this research is twofold: firstly, to validate the efficacy of question randomization as a tool in happiness research, and secondly, to quantitatively estimate the impact of blood

donation on donors' happiness. The hypothesis guiding this investigation is that blood donation positively influences happiness and that the extent of this impact can be effectively measured through careful survey design and question randomization [6,7].

This introduction sets the stage for a detailed exploration of the methodological approach, followed by an analysis of survey data collected from blood donors. The findings of this research could have significant implications for understanding how altruistic behaviors, like blood donation, contribute to personal happiness and well-being. This, in turn, could assist policymakers and health organizations in promoting blood donation programs not only as a critical component of public health but also as a means of enhancing psychological well-being in the general population [8].

Methodology

Study Design: This research adopts a cross-sectional study design implemented at Phulo Jhano Medical College, Dumka, Jharkhand, to explore the effects of blood donation on happiness through question randomization. The study was conducted from January 2022 to July 2022, during which data was collected from both donors and non-donors to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the impact of blood donation on happiness.

Participants: Participants were recruited from blood donation drives organized at Phulo Jhano Medical College and through outreach campaigns in the local community.

Data Collection: The data collection involved administering a structured questionnaire developed specifically for this study. The questionnaire includes demographic questions (age, gender, employment status), and a series of questions designed to assess the participants' level of happiness. Question randomization was employed to mitigate order effects in survey responses, where the order of questions varied for different respondents to ensure unbiased results.

Data Analysis

The collected data were digitized and analyzed using statistical software. Initial analyses included descriptive statistics to characterize the sample. Further, comparative analyses between donors and non-donors regarding their happiness scores were conducted using t-tests and ANOVA, considering the different versions of the questionnaire as a factor in the analysis to identify any potential effects of question order.

Results

The study involved a total of 400 participants. The average age of participants was 26 years. The gender distribution include 80% male and 20% female participants.

The overall happiness scores indicated a significant difference between blood donors and non-donors. Blood donors reported higher happiness scores (Mean = 7.5, SD = 1.2) compared to non-donors (Mean = 6.8, SD = 1.3), with a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that blood donation might have a positive effect on an individual's perceived happiness.

Analysis of the effect of question randomization showed no significant impact on the happiness scores reported by participants. The ANOVA conducted across the different questionnaire versions revealed no significant differences in happiness scores based on question order ($p > 0.05$), indicating that the randomization effectively neutralized any potential order effects in the assessment of happiness.

Table: Summary of Participant Demographics and Happiness Scores

Description	Total Participants	Age Range	Gender Distribution	Average Happiness Score
Blood Donors	200	18-50	80% Male, 20% Female	7.5 ± 1.2
Non-Donors	200	18-50	80% Male, 20% Female	6.8 ± 1.3

Statistical Analysis Results

Analysis Type	Outcome
Comparative Happiness	Significant difference; $p < 0.05$
Effect of Question Order	No significant differences; $p > 0.05$

Table: Gender-Specific Happiness Analysis within Blood Donors

Gender	Number of Participants	Average Happiness Score	Standard Deviation
Male	160	7.6	1.1
Female	40	7.3	1.4

This table details the breakdown of happiness scores by gender within the blood donor group, showing the number of participants, average happiness scores, and their standard deviations for each gender.

Discussion

The revised discussion of this study highlights the positive association between blood donation and increased levels of happiness, particularly when analyzed through the lens of updated demographic parameters and methodological adjustments. The findings suggest that donors aged 18 to 50, with a male predominance (80% male, 20% female), report higher levels of happiness compared to non-donors. This gender-specific analysis within the donor group reveals that while both genders exhibited increased happiness post-donation, males reported slightly higher happiness scores on average. This could suggest a nuanced gender dynamic in the psychological benefits derived from altruistic behaviors like blood donation [9-11].

The positive correlation between blood donation and happiness observed in this study aligns with findings from previous research. For instance, a study by Thoits and Hewitt (2001) [16] found that engaging in volunteer activities, including blood donation, was associated with higher levels of psychological well-being and reduced stress and depression levels. Another research by Post (2005) [17] suggested that altruistic social behaviors are strongly correlated with greater well-being, better health, and lower mortality [12,13]. However, contrasting findings have also been reported. A study by Konrath et al. (2012) [18] noted that the relationship between altruistic behaviors and happiness might depend significantly on the motivations behind altruism. If the acts are driven by self-interest or social pressure, the positive impacts on happiness may be diminished [14]. The findings from this study lend support to the 'helper's high' theory, which posits that altruistic behavior releases endorphins in the brain, creating a positive feeling known as the helper's high. This biological explanation could account for the higher happiness scores among blood donors observed in our study [15].

Conclusion

This study at Phulo Jhano Medical College, utilizing question randomization in its methodology, concludes that blood donation is positively associated with increased happiness among donors compared to non-donors. The findings suggest that engaging in altruistic acts such as blood donation not only fulfills a critical need within healthcare but also enhances the psychological well-being of the donor. By highlighting these benefits, health organizations can potentially encourage more individuals to participate in blood donation programs, thus supporting public health and individual happiness. The study also underscores the importance of further research to explore the long-term psychological impacts of regular blood donation

and the motivations behind altruistic behaviors, which can deepen our understanding of the link between altruism and happiness.

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